

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Bragança, Portugal

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Keywords: Decision-making; Pastoralism; Agricultural data

Session 10: EU PRIMA Online Session – The PAS-AGRO-PAS project

Time: 10:00 – 12:00

Date: 6th September 2024

MODELING THE GROWTH OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN SOFT GOAT'S CHEESE "JBEN" UNDER VARIOUS STORAGE TEMPERATURES

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Outbreaks of listeriosis have been associated with cheese consumption. This study focused on goat's Jben, a traditional Moroccan dairy product, to evaluate and model the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* at different storage temperatures (4–40 °C). Lab-scale Jben samples were prepared using a traditional Moroccan recipe and inoculated with a three-strain cocktail of *L. monocytogenes* at approximately 2 log cfu/g. These inoculated samples (pH = 5.85 ± 0.05, aw = 0.92 ± 0.001) were stored under various isothermal conditions (4, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 °C) and analyzed microbiologically using plate count methodology to quantify pathogen levels. Predictive microbiology models, based on mathematical equations, were used to estimate microbial behavior in the product. The Baranyi model was applied to describe the growth kinetics of cheeses stored at constant temperatures and was integrated with the Ratkowsky model through global regression analysis. This approach correlated *L. monocytogenes* concentrations with storage temperature and time.

Results indicated that the growth potential of *L. monocytogenes* increased with higher storage temperatures. Analysis was performed using MATLAB, and the estimated Ratkowsky model parameters were $a = 0.0066 \text{ Log cfu/h}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C}$, $b = 0.1683 /^{\circ}\text{C}$, $T_{\min} = 2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $T_{\max} = 49.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Growth rates, fitted with the extended Ratkowsky square root model, ranged from 0.001 to 0.0345 log cfu/h at temperatures from 4 to 40 °C. The proposed model aims to predict *L. monocytogenes* growth across a broad range of storage temperatures, providing a basis for informed decisions regarding the microbiological safety of Jben.

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Keywords: Soft goat cheese; *L. monocytogenes*; Predictive microbiology

MODELING THE INHIBITION OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* GROWTH IN FISH PRODUCTS WITH LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS

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The present study aimed to evaluate the potential of several lactic acid bacteria strains, isolated from fish products, as bioprotective cultures against *Listeria monocytogenes* in vacuum-packed, cold-stored fish products. These strains demonstrated their ability to control the growth of *L. monocytogenes* over 21 days of storage and to lower the pH of the medium. To explain the inhibitory effects of the selected lactic acid bacteria on *L. monocytogenes*, microbial interaction was assessed using adapted mathematical models. The kinetic parameters of growth for both microorganisms in monocultures and cocultures were estimated.

The results demonstrate the efficacy of the studied strains in controlling pathogen growth in fish products, achieving an inhibition rate exceeding 40%. The proposed modeling approach aims to reduce the risk of listeriosis associated with the consumption of cold-stored products. It can contribute to establishing a strategy based on bioprotective cultures for fish products.

Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria; Biopreservation; Fish products; *Listeria monocytogenes*; Modeling

ADVANCEMENTS IN BIOMETRIC TECHNIQUES FOR MOROCCAN ARGAN GROVE GOATS

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Biometrics, the science of identifying individuals based on unique physical or behavioral traits, has gained prominence in various fields, including agriculture and animal husbandry. This study highlights the use of biometric techniques in goats, focusing on their importance for breed identification, health monitoring, and livestock management. Goats possess distinctive biometric features such as facial patterns, iris structures, ear shapes, and body measurements, which can be effectively utilized for individual identification. Employing advanced technologies like image processing, machine learning, and 3D scanning allows for the precise and non-invasive capture and analysis of these traits.